

POLICY BRIEF

EU agri-food policies need better indicators

Evidence from scientific literature and agroecology practitioners

Main findings

- To reach **ambitious objectives**, EU agri-food policies need to be designed, monitored and evaluated using **indicators covering the following dimensions of agroecology**: socio-economy, biodiversity, climate change mitigation and adaptation.
- We compared **indicators used in 4 key EU policies** with those considered relevant by **agroecology practitioners for 28 themes identified in the scientific literature** across these 4 dimensions.
- Policy indicators cover **only 25 of the 28 themes**.
- Within covered themes, **key indicators considered relevant by agroecology practitioners are missing**.
- **Many policy indicators are calculated in a suboptimal way**, i.e. at a scale and/or using a definition that is not considered the most relevant by EU agroecology practitioners.

Key policy recommendations

- Enhancing the ability of EU policies to support the expansion of agroecology can be achieved by **adding 16 new policy indicators and revising 6 existing indicators**.
- New indicators concern **farm management and resilience, detailed sources of emissions, temperature regulation, farmers' health,...**
- To increase feasibility and limit monitoring costs, we recommend that these new or revised indicators rely on **available data and methods**.
- Developing such a consolidated set of indicators will be crucial in the context of EU result-based policies, and will enhance **transparency and trust in European policies**.
- By improving its policy indicators, the EU will **better support the expansion of agroecology, decrease EU's dependency on external inputs and enhance food sovereignty**.

Context

- **Agroecology** is key for developing more sustainable food systems.
- Its expansion requires **legal and regulatory frameworks** that enable transformative change.
- The EU has adopted **4 main agricultural and environmental policies aiming towards more sustainable food systems** : CAP, Climate Law, NRR and SML (see figure).
- These policies require a **strong and coherent set of indicators** to ensure that targets are met.

Common Agricultural Policy

Climate Law

Nature Restoration Regulation

Soil Monitoring Law

Objective

Agroecology-TRANSECT, a Horizon Europe project co-financed by the European Commission, Switzerland and the United Kingdom, compared **indicators used to design, monitor and evaluate these 4 EU policies with indicators considered relevant by EU agroecology practitioners**, with a focus on 4 dimensions:

Farm socio-economic performance

Biodiversity

Climate change mitigation

Climate change adaptation

Methodology

- We identified **82 indicators used by these 4 policies**.
- We identified **67 indicators considered relevant by agroecology practitioners** across 11 living laboratories across 10 EU Member States (see map).
- We used the **scientific literature** on agroecology indicators to identify **all relevant themes** within each one of the 4 agroecology dimensions.
- Within each theme, we **compared indicators used by policies and indicators used by agroecology practitioners**, including their **definition** and the **scale** at which they are calculated.

Key results

- Based on the scientific literature, we identified 28 relevant themes across the 4 dimensions.
- Policy indicators covered 25 of the 28 relevant themes**, while practitioner indicators covered 21 themes, with 20 themes being covered by both (see figure). Themes not covered by policy indicators were ‘genetic composition’, ‘species traits’ and ‘temperature regulation’.
- Within the 20 themes covered by both policy indicators and practitioner indicators, **18 themes were covered by policies and practitioners using different sets of indicators**. Such indicator mismatches were most prevalent for ‘farm socio-economic performance’ (7/7 themes) and ‘biodiversity’ (4/4 themes).
- Within the 17 themes for which indicators used by policies were similar to indicators used by agroecology practitioners, **15 themes were covered by policy indicators calculated using definitions that are different from those considered relevant by agroecology practitioners**. For instance, for the theme ‘farm management’, policies use an indicator on ‘pesticide sales’ whereas practitioners use an indicator on ‘pesticide use’.
- All 17 themes were covered by policy indicators calculated at scales that were different from those “targeted” by agroecology practitioners**. Indeed, policy indicators are almost always measured at regional, Member State or EU level, whereas practitioners consider that indicators are relevant at field or farm scale.

All 28 themes across the 4 agroecology dimensions are associated with at least one type of mismatch between policy indicators and practitioner indicators

- Theme not covered by policies
- Theme not covered by practitioners
- Theme covered using different indicators
- Theme covered with similar indicators but different definitions or scales

Conclusion and policy recommendations

- Indicators used in EU policies are **inadequate** to cover the multiple dimensions of agroecology.
- Improving EU policy indicators is particularly crucial in the context of the CAP 2028-2034, which aims to grant **greater flexibility to Member States**, and to move towards **result-based payments**.
- Enhancing the ability of EU policies to support the expansion of agroecology can be achieved by **adding 16 new policy indicators and revising 6 existing indicators** (see list in the table below).
- To increase feasibility and limit monitoring costs, we recommend that these new or revised indicators rely on **available data currently underused** (such as the Farm Sustainability Data Network, Integrated Administration and Control System) **as well as existing methods** (see details in preprint).
- Improving EU policy indicators will help **better support the expansion of agroecology, decrease EU's dependency on external inputs and enhance food sovereignty**. It will also enhance **transparency and trust in European policies**.

Data source	Field	Farm	Region	Main policy concerned
Farm Sustainability Data Network		fertiliser use yield-based pollination index farm resilience capacities farm income diversification	farm income inequalities	CAP and NRR
Integrated Administration and Control System	crop rotational diversity			CAP
National health insurance systems			farmers' health	CAP
Data on GHG emissions			emissions fertiliser and pesticides (rev.) emissions imported deforestation emissions purchased livestock feed emissions food systems	CAP and Climate Law
Observatory of costs, margins and trading practices in the agri-food chain			farm share of consumer spending on food	CAP
Remote-sensing products	mowing intensity soil carbon (rev.)	hedgerow density (rev.) carbon storage in hedgerows		CAP, NRR and SML
Pesticide sales/use	pesticide use (rev.)			CAP
Monitoring schemes			grassland butterfly index (rev.) soil fauna (rev.) temperature regulation weed diversity pest regulation	CAP, NRR and SML

About this policy brief

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Further reading: Blaix, C., Zagaria, C., Finch, E.A., Pe'er, G., Dumont, B., Sirami, C. (preprint) Indicators used by EU policies do not sufficiently match those needed to expand agroecology. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.6814006>